

20IND11 MetHyInfra

**Deliverable D6: Good practice
guide on the setting up of a
simulation (e.g. a CFD model in
OpenFOAM) of critical nozzle flow
for high pressure hydrogen**

DELIVERABLE D6

Lead partner: ESI

Authors: Sonja Schmelter, Sebastian Weiss, Jiri Polansky
Confidentiality: Public
Submission date: 31.05.2024
Due date: 31.05.2024
Revision: 1.0

methyinfra.ptb.de

This project "Metrology infrastructure for high-pressure gas and liquefied hydrogen flows" (MetHyInfra) has received funding from the EMPIR programme co-financed by the Participating States and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

Deliverable D6: Good practice guide on the setting up of a simulation (e.g. a CFD model in OpenFOAM) of critical nozzle flow for high pressure hydrogen		
Funding European Metrology Program for Innovation and Research		Grant agreement no: 20IND11
Project name Metrology infrastructure for high-pressure gas and liquified hydrogen flows		Project short name MetHyInfra
Author(s) Sonja Schmelter PTB sonja.schmelter@ptb.de Sebastian Weiss PTB sebastian.weiss@ptb.de Jiri Polansky ESI jiri.polansky@esi-group.com		Pages 12 pages
<p>Summary</p> <p>This deliverable was written as part of activity 3.3.5 from the EMPIR Metrology infrastructure for high-pressure gas and liquified hydrogen flows (MetHyInfra) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing metrological infrastructure and traceability for high pressure hydrogen flow meter calibration (1000 bar / 3.6 kg/min), fuel cells applications (4 kg/h, 30 bar) and liquid hydrogen. For more details about this project please visit methyinfra.ptb.de.</p> <p>This deliverable is a good practice guide on how to set up a CFD model in OpenFOAM for the simulation of high pressure hydrogen flow through critical nozzles. It is based on the presentation [8] given by Sebastian Weiss at the <i>Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) Workshop</i> of the MetHyInfra project.</p>		
Confidentiality		Public

This project (20IND11 MetHyInfra) has received funding from the EMPIR programme co-financed by the Participating States and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

The EMPIR initiative is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the EMPIR Participating States

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Geometry creation	2
3	Mesh creation	3
4	Numerical set-up	4
4.1	Boundary conditions	5
4.2	Turbulence model	6
4.3	Real gas model	7
4.4	Numerical settings	7
5	Post-processing	9

1 Introduction

This deliverable describes how to set up a model for simulating high pressure hydrogen flow in critical nozzles in OpenFOAM. In the following sections, the different pre-processing steps that are necessary to set up such a simulation as well as the post-processing steps that are required to check the simulation results will be presented. They will be described using the tutorial case [8] presented at the *Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) Workshop* of the MetHyInfra project in Borås, Sweden as an example. Fig. 1 shows the pre-processing steps (in the left picture) and illustrates which parts of the OpenFOAM folder structure will be touched by those steps (in the scheme on the right).

Figure 1: Pre-processing steps that are necessary to set up a simulation in OpenFOAM and corresponding files in the OpenFOAM folder structure that need to be edited.

This good practice guide is structured as follows:

Section 2 describes how the nozzle contour can be created using a Python script. It covers the geometry creation for ideal shapes (toroidal and cylindrical) according to the ISO standard 9300 [1] as well as non-ideal nozzle shapes coming from dimensional measurements of real nozzles. In Section 3, the creation of hexahedral meshes using the *blockMesh* utility of OpenFOAM will be described. Section 4 gives an overview of the numerical set-up. It is divided into several subsections that explain in detail how to define boundary conditions, choose an appropriate turbulence model, apply a real gas model, and select discretization schemes. In

Section 5, it will be described how to check the convergence of the simulation and how to analyze the relevant simulation results.

2 Geometry creation

This section describes how the geometry of a nozzle can be created. The nozzle contour needs to be provided in a specific format so that it can later be used by the meshing tool. For this, a Python script is provided, which allows to create ideal toroidal and cylindrical nozzles (according to the ISO standard [1]) as well as measured ones. The ideal toroidal and cylindrical shapes can be created using the functions $Tor_ideal(l, al, nz)$ and $Cyl_ideal(l, al, nz)$, respectively, where l is the (dimensionless) length of the nozzle in throat diameters d , al is the diffuser angle (in degrees), and nz is the number of points used for the discrete representation of the nozzle geometry, see Fig. 2 for illustration.

Figure 2: Ideal toroidal (top) and cylindrical (bottom) nozzle contours created by the functions $Tor_ideal(9d, 4^\circ, 1000)$ and $Cyl_ideal(9d, 4^\circ, 1000)$, respectively.

Measured nozzle contours can be created by using the function $Meas_CFVN(meas_data, NType, l, n_in, n_out)$, where $meas_data$ is the name of the file containing the measured data, $NType$ defines the type of nozzle ($NType = 1$ for toroidal and $NType = 0$ for cylindrical), n_in is the index of the position, up to which the radius of the inlet circle of the nozzle is determined, and n_out is the index of the position, where the calculation of the outlet slope starts. Fig. 3 illustrates the function and its input parameters.

Figure 3: Measured nozzle contour created by the function $Meas_CFVN$ ('Cyl_D1_meas.txt', 0, 9d, 40, 20).

All three functions (Tor_ideal , Cyl_ideal , and $Meas_CFVN$) return two vectors containing the z - and y -coordinate of the nozzle geometry. Here, z denotes the axial and y the radial position of the nozzle contour. Furthermore, the functions return the index i of the position (z/y), where the throat is located (i.e., the position of the smallest diameter, which is normalized to 1).

These data are then used as input to the function $create_geometry_file$ ($name, z, y, i$), which creates the geometry for the OpenFOAM simulation.

3 Mesh creation

Using the geometry from Section 2 as input, the OpenFOAM utility $blockMesh$ can be used to create a block-structured mesh. For this, the file $blockMeshDict$ needs to be edited. Fig. 4 explains the different parameters that can be adapted in this file.

Figure 4: Illustration of parameters used in the file $blockMeshDict$ to create an appropriate mesh for a given nozzle contour.

A3.3.5 – Good practice guide on the setting up of a simulation of critical nozzle flow for high pressure hydrogen

In this example, the nozzle contour file `Meas_Cyl.out` has been generated by the function `create_geometry_file` as shown in the previous Section 2. The size of the nozzle can be set using the scaling factor `sc`. With the parameter `li`, the inlet domain can be defined. For the creation of the mesh, the three parameters `cy`, `cz`, and `gy` define the number of cells in the radial and in the axial direction and the grading in the radial direction, respectively. The grading parameter `gy`, defined as the ratio of the height of the cell in the core region `t2` and of the cell at the wall `t1`, controls the mesh resolution close to the wall. The mesh is then created using the following command:

```
blockMesh && extrudeMesh &
```

The metrics of the mesh (skewness, orthogonality, aspect ratio, etc.) can be checked with the command:

```
checkMesh
```

4 Numerical set-up

This section describes how to set up an OpenFOAM simulation for high-pressure hydrogen flow in CFVNs. The OpenFOAM version v2012 [6] is used in this good practice guide. The cylindrical nozzle displayed in Fig. 5 will be used as an example. In the following subsections, it will be described how to set the initial and boundary

Figure 5: Description of the tutorial case used for illustrating the choice of parameters when setting up a CFD simulation in OpenFOAM.

conditions correctly, how to choose an appropriate turbulence model, how to use a real gas model, and how to select discretization schemes.

4.1 Boundary conditions

For the numerical simulation of the flow in a CFVN as illustrated in Fig. 5, total pressure and temperature need to be prescribed at the inlet: $p_0 = 200$ bar and $T_0 = 300$ K. At the outlet, a boundary condition for the static pressure is used: $p_s = 100$ bar. The walls are assumed to be adiabatic and with no slip. Hence, we set $U = 0$ there and use zero-gradient boundary conditions for pressure and temperature. To save computational time, only a wedge of 5° is simulated, assuming rotational symmetry around the z -axis. Therefore, we prescribe symmetry boundary conditions at the front and back. The initial conditions are set as follows: $p(0) = 200$ bar, $T(0) = 300$ K, and $U(0) = 0$.

Fig. 6 summarizes the prescribed boundary conditions for the tutorial case. Note

Figure 6: Summary of initial and boundary conditions set for pressure p , temperature T , and velocity U for the tutorial case, see Fig. 5.

that the dimensions of the variables p , T , and U are prescribed in the parameter `dimensions`. Here, the numbers given at the i th position in the vector denote the exponents of the corresponding SI units, where $i = 1$ stands for kg (mass), $i = 2$ for m (length), $i = 3$ for s (time), $i = 4$ for K (temperature), $i = 5$ for mol (quantity), $i = 6$ for A (current), and $i = 7$ for cd (luminous intensity). The unit of the variable is then given by multiplying all the SI units with the respective exponent given at i th position in the `dimensions` vector. As an example for pressure, `[1 -1 -2 0 0 0 0]` stands for $\text{kg}^1 \times \text{m}^{-1} \times \text{s}^{-2} \times \text{K}^0 \times \text{mol}^0 \times \text{A}^0 \times \text{cd}^0 = \text{Pa}$.

4.2 Turbulence model

The turbulence model is selected in the *turbulenceProperties* file (see Fig. 1 for OpenFOAM folder structure). Fig. 7 shows how the k - ω SST model, see [4, 5], can be selected for the simulation of turbulent nozzle flow. For further information on different turbulence modeling approaches for sonic nozzle flow, see [9].

Figure 7: Example of an appropriate turbulence model and corresponding parameter selection for the simulation of a sonic nozzle in OpenFOAM.

When using a turbulence model, additional equations are solved besides the equations for velocity, pressure, and temperature. Hence, initial and boundary conditions also need to be prescribed for these variables. For the SST model, these are turbulent kinetic energy k , turbulent specific dissipation rate ω , turbulent viscosity ν_t , and turbulent thermal diffusivity α_t . Fig. 8 summarizes appropriate initial and boundary conditions for these parameters. For further details, see [8].

Figure 8: Example of appropriate initial and boundary conditions for the turbulence parameters in the SST model for the simulation of a sonic nozzle in OpenFOAM.

4.3 Real gas model

When flows of hydrogen at high pressure (or low temperature) are modeled, a real gas model needs to be used. In [10], new correlation equations for relevant hydrogen properties have been developed based on the Reference Fluid Thermodynamic and Transport Properties Database (REFPROP) [3, 2]. These equations have been implemented in OpenFOAM. The developed real gas model can be downloaded from [7].

In OpenFOAM, the real gas model is selected in the *thermophysicalProperties* file (see Fig. 1 for OpenFOAM folder structure). The settings that need to be prescribed in this file are shown in Fig. 9 for real gas (left) and ideal gas (right) using the flow of hydrogen through a CFVN as an example (see Fig. 5 for illustration of the considered example).

Figure 9: Depending on the type of model used, real gas settings (left) or ideal gas settings (right) need to be prescribed in the file *thermophysicalProperties*.

4.4 Numerical settings

Numerical settings are prescribed in the following files: *controlDict*, *fvSchemes*, and *fvSolution* (see Fig. 1 for OpenFOAM folder structure).

In the *controlDict* file, the type of solver, start and end time of the simulation, time step size of the simulation, and parameters to adjust the time step size during the simulation are set. Furthermore, the file includes several parameters that specify how often, to which files and in which format output is written. Functions (e.g. for calculating the mass flow rate, Mach number, or density distribution at defined time intervals) can also be defined in this file. For details, see [8].

A3.3.5 – Good practice guide on the setting up of a simulation of critical nozzle flow for high pressure hydrogen

The numerical schemes used for the discretization in time and space are set in the `fvSchemes` file, see Fig. 10 for an example.

<pre>fvSchemes { default Euler; Euler; } gradSchemes { default Gauss linear; } divSchemes { default none; div(phi,U) Gauss limitedLinearV 1; div(phi,a) Gauss limitedLinear 1; div(phi,p) Gauss limitedLinear 1; div(phi,K) Gauss limitedLinear 1; div(phi,omega) Gauss upwind; div(phi,epsilon) Gauss upwind; div(((rho*muEff)/dev2((grad(O)))) Gauss linear; } laplacianSchemes { default Gauss linear corrected; } interpolationSchemes { default linear; } surfaceNormalGradients { default corrected; } wallDist { method meshQuality; }</pre>	<p>Time schemes $\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\phi)$</p> <p>Gradient schemes $\nabla(\phi)$</p> <p>Divergence schemes $\nabla \cdot (Q)$</p> <p>Laplacian schemes $\nabla^2(\phi)$</p> <p>Interpolation schemes</p> <p>Surface-normal gradient schemes</p> <p>Wall distance calculation method</p>	<p>Keywords:</p> <p>General:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> phi: Flux across cell faces Gauss: Gaussian integration <p>Time scheme:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Euler: First order, implicit, bounded <p>Discretization schemes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> linear: Second order, unbounded limitedLinear: First / second order, unbounded upwind: First order, bounded <p>Correction scheme:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> corrected: Second order, non-orthogonality <p>Remember:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> First order: bounded / stable but diffusive Second order: accurate but might oscillate
---	---	--

Figure 10: Left: example of suitable time and space discretization schemes for the numerical simulation of high pressure hydrogen flow in CFVNs. Right: explanation of key words used in the `fvSchemes` file.

In the `fvSolution` file, the solvers, tolerances, and number of iterations for the solution of the discretized equations are set. Fig. 11 (left) gives an example of this file for the case that the PIMPLE algorithm is used for the coupling between pressure and velocity. A scheme describing the procedure of the PIMPLE algorithm is shown

<pre>solvers { "rho" { solver diagonal; } "p" { solver smoothSolver; smoother GaussSeidel; tolerance 1e-08; relTol 0; } "(U a K)" { \$solver; \$tolerance 1e-07; } "(k omega)" { \$solver; \$tolerance 1e-08; } } PIMPLE { nOuterCorrectors 3; nCorrectors 1; nNonOrthogonalCorrectors 0; }</pre>	<p>Diagonal solver for explicit systems</p> <p>Symmetric Gauss-Seidel solver</p> <p>PIMPLE algorithm</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pressure-velocity coupling algorithm fulfilling momentum and continuity equation in each time step <p>nOuterCorrectors: number of momentum predictor (outer) loops</p> <p>nCorrectors: number of velocity corrector (inner) loops</p> <p>nNonOrthogonalCorrectors: number of pressure (inner) loops</p>	
--	--	--

Figure 11: Left: example of suitable time and space discretization schemes for the numerical simulation of high pressure hydrogen flow in CFVNs. Right: explanation of key words used in the `fvSolution` file.

in Fig. 11 (right).

To start the simulation (serial run) and write a log file, use the command:

```
sonicFoam > log &
```

For a parallel run, the domain needs to be decomposed into subdomains first.

Hence, the following commands can be used (for a parallel run on four processors, for example):

```
decomposePar &
mpirun -np 4 sonicFoam -parallel > log &
reconstructPar &
```

Furthermore, the number of subdomains and the decomposition method need to be specified in the *decomposeParDict* file. For further details, see [8].

5 Post-processing

Once the simulation has been completed, it is necessary to check the convergence of the simulation as the first post-processing step. The starting point is the *log* file that has been written during the simulation. Fig. 12 shows where this file can be found in the OpenFOAM folder structure. With the command:

Figure 12: Left: post-processing steps that are necessary to check the convergence of a simulation, to calculate the discharge coefficient, and to visualize the flow field. Right: corresponding files in the OpenFOAM folder structure, where the results can be found.

```
foamLog log &
```

the residual data are extracted from the log file and are stored in a separate folder */logs*. The residuals should drop and reach below an acceptable level as an indica-

A3.3.5 – Good practice guide on the setting up of a simulation of critical nozzle flow for high pressure hydrogen

tion for a converged solution. Furthermore, the mass flow rate, as the most important result parameter of this simulation, needs to be monitored to make sure that it does not change significantly with time. Smaller oscillations, however, usually cannot be avoided and are acceptable.

Once the convergence is checked, the discharge coefficient of the simulation can be calculated as described in more detail in [8]. Further post-processing steps can be the creation of surface, contour or line plots. Fig. 13 graphically explains how contour and surface plots for the Mach number and the compressibility factor can be created with *ParaView*.

Figure 13: Graphical explanation how the flow field in the CFVN can be visualized by means of surface and contour plots in *ParaView*.

Fig. 14 describes how to create numerical Schlieren pictures using the gradients of density. Such pictures can be used to visualize the shock wave patterns within the nozzle and to compare the simulation results qualitatively with experimental Schlieren images.

For a quantitative comparison between different simulations or with experimental data, line plots can be helpful. The creation of these kind of plots in *ParaView* is illustrated in Fig. 15. As an example, the velocity is plotted at three different axial locations within the nozzle throat. The information of the line plots can be stored as text files for further investigations of the flow data, e.g. the calculation of the displacement or momentum thickness.

Numerical Schlieren

Gradient of Unstructured DataSet filter

1. Set density gradient

2. Apply X Ray colormap

3. Adjust Min. and Max. values

Experimental Schlieren
(for qualitative comparison)

Source: S. Matsuo et al., "Effects of Supersonic Nozzle Geometry on Characteristics of Shock Wave Structure", Open Journal of Fluid Dynamics, Vol. 2 No. 4A, 2012.

Figure 14: Graphical explanation how to create numerical Schlieren pictures of the shock wave structure in a CFVN using *ParaView*.

Plot Over Line filter

1. Define the line location

2. Select the velocity

3. Save line data as text file

Figure 15: Graphical explanation how to create line plots in *ParaView* and how to save the corresponding data as text file.

References

- [1] EN ISO 9300. ISO 9300 - Measurement of gas flow by means of critical flow Venturi nozzles, 2005.
- [2] M. L. Huber, E. W. Lemmon, I. H. Bell, and M. O. McLinden. The NIST REFPROP database for highly accurate properties of industrially important fluids. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, June 2022. doi:10.1021/acs.iecr.2c01427.
- [3] E. W. Lemmon, I. H. Bell, M. L. Huber, and M. O. McLinden. NIST Reference Fluid Thermodynamic and Transport Properties Database (REFPROP) Version 10 - SRD 23, 2018.
- [4] F. R. Menter. Two-equation eddy-viscosity turbulence models for engineering applications. *AIAA Journal*, 32(8):1598–1605, Aug. 1994. doi:10.2514/3.12149.
- [5] F. R. Menter, M. Kuntz, and R. Langtry. Ten Years of Industrial Experience with the SST Turbulence Model. *Turbulence, Heat and Mass Transfer*, 4, Jan. 2003.
- [6] OpenFOAM (v2012). OpenFOAM - the Open Source CFD Toolbox - User Guide (Version v2012). OpenCFD Limited, Dec. 2020.
- [7] S. Weiss. Code of the hydrogen real gas model implementation into OpenFOAM. <https://gitlab1.ptb.de/methyinfra/hydrogen-real-gas-model>, 2022.
- [8] S. Weiss. Tutorial case of a critical nozzle: "FROM Adjusting the mesh TO visualizing the flow field". Part 3 of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) Workshop of the MetHyInfra project, 15 June 2023. URL https://www.methyinfra.ptb.de/fileadmin/documents/empir-2021/methyinfra/documents/Computational_Fluid_Dynamics_Workshop_Part_3.pdf.
- [9] S. Weiss and S. Schmelter. Suitable turbulence models for high-pressure hydrogen flows through critical nozzles. Report (A3.1.3) of EMPIR project "Metrology infrastructure for high-pressure gas and liquified hydrogen flows" (MetHyInfra)., March 2022. URL https://www.methyinfra.ptb.de/fileadmin/documents/empir-2021/methyinfra/documents/A3.1.3_Suitable_turbulence_models_for_high-pressure.pdf.
- [10] S. Weiss, J. Polansky, M. Bär, K. Oberleithner, and S. Schmelter. Derivation and validation of a reference data-based real gas model for hydrogen. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 48(61):23645–23654, 2023. ISSN 0360-3199. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.03.073>.